

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Ume**FIRST NAME:** lfeanyi**PROGRAM CODE:** MIPH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- A good academic writing draws from other writers and researcher's work; as a result, extensive reading and researching is needed. The researcher should ask the following rhetoric questions except?**
 - What do I need to read to be able to answer the essay question?
 - Is the material useful to the topic?
 - What do I need do to finish the research work on time?**¹
 - Can I use the material to support my answer?
- According to Turabian, the first obligation of a good researcher is to fully and accurately cite the sources of his work thereby making it easier for readers to find them. Which of the reasons below best describes why citing sources ascribes legitimacy to a researcher's work?**

¹ Euclid University, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1* (Euclid University: <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf> Assessed January 26, 2020), 3.

- Readers trust works with reliable evidence whose sources are easy to find.²**
- Research work that are well written in either the United State or the United Kingdom English style are equally accepted as a good academic writing.
- Because citing sources is a requirement in academic writing.
- Essays based on experimental writing also offers similar legitimacy and accepted by readers.

3. **How does Turabian best describe a research argument?**

- Intimidating an opponent into silence or submission with your superior knowledge.
- Opposing ones claim.
- Presenting your argument in a manner that is impossible for anyone to dispute.
- An amiable conversation in which you and your imagined readers reason together to solve a problem whose solution they don't yet fully accept until they see good reasons based on reliable evidences.³**

4. **The three founding treaties of the European Union (formerly European Communities) are:**

- ECSC Treaty, Merger Treaty and Single European Act.
- ECSC Treaty, EEC Treaty and Euratom Treaty.⁴**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th ed (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 25.

³ Turabian, L Kate, 36.

⁴ European Union, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in European Commission*. 7th ed (Retrieved from: <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/xitMjHAGfJ/> Assessed January 26, 2020), 52.

- Single European Act, Greenland Treaty and Treaty of Nice.
 - Greenland Treaty, EEC Treaty and Treaty of Amsterdam.
5. **The European Central Bank is the central bank for the EU's single currency, and its main responsibility is to maintain its purchasing power and price stability. What is the EU's single currency called?**
- Euro.**⁵
 - Dollar.
 - Pound.
 - Yen.
6. **Which of these represent one of the three categories of internal financial funding mechanisms of the European Union and its institutions?**
- Contributions from member states.
 - Grants from funding agencies.
 - Member states' gross national income.**⁶
 - Humanitarian support.
7. **According to Writing Source, which of the following is key to developing effective writing?**

⁵ European Union, 67-68.

⁶ European Union, 69-70.

- Good ideas, clear organization, effective word choice.**⁷
- Choosing your topic.
- Having prior knowledge or understanding of the topic.
- Natural flair for writing.
8. **Prewriting is the first step in the writing process, which of the following describes essential activities carried out during prewriting?**
- Identifying available avenues for publishing of the work.
- Determining the type of citation to be used.
- Being able to type your work in a computer.
- Selecting a specific subject and gathering information about it.**⁸
9. **There are two general sources of information – primary and secondary source. Which of these is a source of primary information?**
- Internet.
- Observation and participation.**⁹
- Television.
- Encyclopedia.
10. **Which of these are associated with common errors made in writing research papers?**

⁷ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Great Source Education Group, a division of Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999), 19.

⁸ Sebranek, Kemper and Meyer, 46.

⁹ Sebranek, Kemper and Meyer, 261-263.

- Proofreading before turning in the research paper.
- Wrong grammar, misspelling and inaccurate words or phrases.**¹⁰
- Adequate and proper citation.
- Verb tense – using past tense to describe that have happened, and present tense for generally accepted facts.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, a division of Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.
- European Union. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in European Commission*. 7th . 2011.
- Euclid University. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015.
- Euclid University. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Euclid University, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4* (Euclid University: <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/YIJXVLgPv0/> Assessed January 26, 2020), 1.